
REVIEW: *PRAYERS IN THE WIND* BY TSHE RING

NOR BU ཚེ་རིང་ནོར་བུ། (CIREN LUOBU 次仁罗布)

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Ciren Luobu 次仁罗布. 2015. *Jiyu Fengzhong* 祭语风中 [*Prayers in the Wind*]. Beijing 北京: Zhongyi Chubanshe 中译出版社 [Chinese Translation Press]. 442 pp. ISBN 978-7-4225-6 (paperback 39.8RMB).

Tshe ring nor bu ཚེ་རིང་ནོར་བུ། (Blo brtan ལྷོ་བརྟན།, translator). 2018. *Rlung khrod kyi mchod sbyin* ལྷུང་ཁྲོད་ཀྱི་མཚན་སྒྲིབ། [*Prayers in the Wind*]. Lha sa ལྷ་ས།: Bod ljongs bod yig dpe rnying dpe skrun khang བོད་ཚོར་ལ་བོད་ཡིག་དཔེ་སྐྱེད་དང་སྐྱུར་ཁུངས། [Tibetan Ancient Books Press]. 561 pp. ISBN978-7-5700-0110-1 (paperback 68RMB).

Tsering Norbu (Joshua Dyer, translator; Bruce Humes, copyeditor). 2019. *Prayers in the Wind*. [*Rlung khrod kyi mchod sbyin* ལྷུང་ཁྲོད་ཀྱི་མཚན་སྒྲིབ།]. Beijing 北京: Zhongyi Chubanshe 中译出版社 [Chinese Translation Press]. 586 pp. ISBN 978-7-5001-9 (paperback 169RMB); Amazon World Copyrights Publishing Group Inc., ASINBo8V1HC6ZJ (Kindle Edition USD9.99).

The front page of the English translation of *Prayers in the Wind* notes: "...Tibetan writer Tsering Norbu [Tshe ring nor bu] has been featuring [sic] on China's 'Best Novel' and 'Best Short Story' charts since 2006." Born in Lha sa in 1965, the author was educated locally, graduating in 1986 from Tibet University with a BA in Tibetan literature. He subsequently taught Tibetan at a senior middle school in Chab mdo (Changdu) City for two years and later worked at the

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Post and Telecommunication School of Tibet. In 1989, his job was transferred to Sne mo (Nimu) County. His Chinese-language novel, *The Ferryman of Nor rtse*, was published in *Tibetan Literature* in 1992, receiving positive comments from the editor, Li Jiajun.¹ Earlier, several of his short stories, prose compositions, and poems were published in Tibetan magazines such as *Tibetan Youth* and *Lha sa Evening Paper*.²

While an editor for the *Tibet Daily* in 2004, he received an opportunity to attend the Lu Xun Literature Academy for literary skill training. In late 2005, his job was transferred to the Tibetan Literature Association, where he furthered his literature creation endeavors. His short story, *Killer*, was included in China's Novel Charts in 2006, listed in Xiaoshuo Xuankan 'Selected Stories' Quadrennial National Excellent Stories, and included in *21 Shiji Zhongguo Dangdai Wenxue '21st Century Chinese Literature'*. *Killer* also won a Gold Award of the 5th Qomolangma Literature and Art Award. Later, Tibetan auteur, Pad ma tshe brtan (Pema Tsedan), adapted *Killer* in his film, *Jinpa* (2018; see FT³ 2).

His mid-length novel, *Realm*, was published in the second issue of *National Literature* in 2007, winning the 5th Tibet New Century Literary Award in 2008, and translated into English by Krysta Close and Dong Rui ('Brug mo skyid 2019:532). *The Released Sheep* and *America* were published in the 4th issue of the Chinese magazine, *Fangcao 'Fragrant Grass'*, in 2009. The former was included in *Xiaoshuo Yuebao 'Fiction Monthly'* and listed in the charts of China's Latest Contemporary Fiction in 2009, translated into Korean, and won the 5th Lu Xun Literature Prize in 2009, while *America* was selected for inclusion in both *China's 2009 Short Story Collection (2009 Nian Zhongguo Duanpian Xiaoshuoji)* and *2009 China's Best Short Stories. Possession*, a short story, won the National Literature Award in 2011.⁴

¹ <https://bit.ly/3EuNwZG> 19 September 2021 provides a more complete Tibetan-language introduction.

² <https://bit.ly/3omPaXl> 5 December 2021 introduces the author.

³ Here and later, "FT" indicates "footnote."

⁴ <https://bit.ly/3EydzPC> 19 September 2021 provides a detailed introduction.

'Brug mo skyid reports: "Currently, Ciren Luobu [Tshe ring nor bu] is Executive Chief Editor of *Tibetan Literature*, a member of the China Writers Association Committee, and Vice-Chair of the Tibet Writers Association" (2019:532).

Prayers in the Wind was published in the third issue of *Fangcao* in 2015. After its release by the Chinese Translation Press in August 2015, there was a noteworthy reaction in the field of Chinese Literature (Hu and Ciren Luobu 2016:117).

In an interview on the media platform, Mi chung kha bde 'The Voluble Little Man',¹ the author notes that his new novel, *Wusizang [Dbus gtsang] 'Central Tibet'*, will soon be released and adds that *Prayers in the Wind* has been translated into Kazakh and *The Released Sheep* has been translated into Hungarian.

Tshe ring nor bu mainly employs the first-person to narrate the difficult life experiences of the protagonist, 'Jig med dbang grags, in the 1950s-1960s. The author occasionally inserts an omniscient point of view to provide panoramic life scenes. For his multiple combinations of points of view, Liu (2016:196) notes:

第二人称叙述，明显具有反常规阅读经验，又具有类似喜剧中的"第四堵墙"的效应，意味着观众称为叙事的参与者，接受了参与叙述的行为。

The second-person narrative is an apparent abnormal reading experience but has a similar effect of 'breaking the fourth wall'² in theatre, allowing readers to participate in the narrative acts (my translation).

Moreover, Zhou (2017:109) comments that multiple layers of the spatial narrative of *Prayers in the Wind* differ from the temporal patterns required by the grand narrative this novel employs.

This book consists of two parts. Part One has twelve chapters, and

¹ See <https://bit.ly/3Kjb5Yq> 18 January 2022 or the video interview.

² "...an invisible barrier known in literature as the fourth wall – the barrier between the characters and the audience" (<https://bit.ly/3pGrsoz> 3 December 2021).

Part Two has ten chapters. The story begins near a sky burial platform, where the main protagonist is visited by Zhi 'od kun dga' nyi ma, a reincarnate *bla ma*, whose former life was 'Jig med dbang grags' tutor. Zhi 'od kun dga' nyi ma struggles to comprehend the life experience of his previous incarnation and the protagonist through a few hours of interview with the main character, 'Jig med dbang grags, who passes away in the first chapter of Part One after meeting his tutor's reincarnation and asking the young reincarnated *bla ma* to perform *pho ba* 'rituals to achieve rebirth in a buddha realm' during his final moments.

Tshe ring nor bu aptly describes the *pho ba* experienced - one was performing as the other moved into a state of unconsciousness, making the first chapter of Part One both the start and end of the story.

Part One's 'Chapter Two' focuses on the protagonist's life history with occasional comments from the interviewer. During the period of chaos, the People's Liberation Army moved to Lha sa, where Tibetan elites, commoners, and monks fled to India from their homeland. 'Jig med dbang grags, his tutor, and two other monk pupils (Lho brag nor bzang and Rdo rje gyal mtshan) opted to follow after consulting the tutor's *yi dam* 'tutelary deity'.

As they trek to India, they visit one of the tutor's patrons at his manor. The young master, Ser tang, and his daughter, Lady Gser thang, live a tranquil life in stark contrast to the chaos in Lha sa City. The narrator comments, "Time stood still at Sertang Manor. It was a utopia that existed apart from the tumultuous world we were living in" (English version:81).

Education and travel abroad led the young master of Gser tang Manor to embrace modern ideas, including democracy, the Western political system, and modern technology. At his manor, Gser thang Master and his steward sip brandy and other drinks in various shaped glasses during a banquet to host Zhi 'od kun dga' nyi ma and his pupils. Young Master's daughter and her friends ride British bicycles. Meanwhile, Ser tang Master has reduced taxes on his serfs, given house servants some of his family-owned fields, and bought metal plows to ease laborers' work.

Young Master enthusiastically hoped for social changes leading to equality among all people. Common laborers would become independent and no longer enslaved people. He praised Chairman Mao in his poems as a bright warm sun bringing glory, happiness, and wealth to Snow Land people. He earnestly believed it was a perfect time for ordinary Tibetans, even though his family's property was confiscated; his father was forced to do construction labor; Young Master himself was dismissed from his editor job and forced to confess exploitations he committed in previous times; and he and Lady Gser thang were forced to wear hats of humiliation, brought before crowds, and criticized. The narrator describes this mortifying scene:

...A paper hat scrawled with slogans was perched on her [Lady Sertang's] head. "Overthrow the Ox-ghosts and Snake-demons! Overthrow the anti-Revolutionaries!" Around her neck hung a garland of old Tibetan money and a plaque with her name on it... Master Sertang appeared at the end of the procession beating a pair of cymbals as he walked. They [the Red Guards] had dressed him in a brocade gown and a paper hat like the one Lady Sertang [Gser thang] wore... a list of crimes was hung around his neck... (English version:467).

Because of her father's aristocratic identity, his daughter was not allowed to participate in dancing, singing, and stage plays that now focused on political propaganda. Later, she desperately cut relations with her father and married a physically unattractive working-class man, thus avoiding additional criticism and earning a secure job. However, when the narrator later met her, she was divorced and planning to go aboard where her sister worked.

When Liu (2016) read Young Master's poems praising Mao and the Communist Party, he recalled historical Chinese poets who praised Mao:

文学的存在状况难以一语说清，时代的谎言就是如此，而写下这类诗歌的主人的命运几起几伏，跌宕不已，我们无法区分现实还是文学，历史的文本和想象的文学聚在同一时空，是特殊时代的特殊产物，也是特殊意境中特殊表现形式，具有极强的寓言色彩和反讽意味。

It is challenging to present the existence of literature, the absurdity of an era, and the travails of those who composed these poems - we cannot discern if it is reality or fiction. When historical text and fiction are combined in a single unity of space and time, it could be understood as a special production of a special era... intensely colored by fable and irony (Liu 2016:199).

Divination and oracles have played a vital role in Tibetan society, especially during times of crisis, justifying a close examination of the motivation behind the human flight portrayed in *Prayers in the Wind*. For example, a prominent Tibetan leader consulted a Buddhist oracle when he was about to leave Tibet. Similarly, the narrator and his *bla ma* consulted his teacher's *yi dam* when the political situation in Lha sa worsened.

The author emphasized in an interview that *Prayers in the Wind* is not an intentional presentation of Tibetan culture but rather authentic Tibetan daily life (Hu and Ciren Luobu 2016:121).¹

The monk refugees continue toward the Indian border after several days at Gser thang Manor. They were stopped by Tibetan soldiers on a steep mountainside and forced to hand over their only horse and baggage on a steep mountainside. Lho brag nor bzang does not quickly give the package on his back to a soldier, who grabs and pulls it, sending a candy tin to the ground that opens, spilling jewels. Rdo rje rgya mtshan rushes over and strikes the soldier. Irritated, the soldier kicks him in the chest, sending him tumbling down the steep mountain to his death.

After the monk's death, the *bla ma* decides to meditate in a mountain cave near a monastery and orders the two pupils to return to their Lha sa monastery, which they do, though the narrator is reluctant to leave his *bla ma*. As they return, the narrator

¹ Cabezón observes that close observation of Tibetans in their daily life reveals that many engage in various religious activities:

If you live near a monastery, chances are that you will awaken to the sound of a gong calling monks to their morning prayer assembly or *tsog* (*tshogs*). Even if you live far from a monastery, you may well be roused from sleep by the high-pitched clanging of someone ringing a ritual bell, or by the soft murmur of neighbors reciting *khandön* (*kha 'don*), their daily ritual commitments... (2010:01).

and Lho brag nor bzung are apprehended by Chinese soldiers and taken to Lha sa in an old truck full of captured Tibetan soldiers and refugees. In Lha sa, the narrator and Lho brag nor bzung are separated and assigned tasks in different work units.

Upon his release some months later, the narrator goes to his father's house, hoping to find his father and brother, but the house is locked, and neighbors do not know their whereabouts. He then walks to his monastery with *tshwa tshwa* 'miniature clay stupas' made from some of the deceased monk's remains and places them on a hill behind the monastery.

Most monks left the monastery, joining groups to learn new policies established by the Communist Party. Other monks became laymen. Only a few aged monks pray, debate, and chant at the monastery. The narrator stays in his monastery room till he has no more food, then goes to Lha sa City, where he is classified as a proletariat by Communist officers and assigned a job registering residents.

At the beginning of Part Two, soldiers are recruited from Lha sa residents to support the battlefield at the Indian border. The narrator also joins, which allows him to visit his teacher in the mountain cave, but he learns he has passed away.

After cremating his teacher's corpse, he finds relics among the ashes. He returns home with his teacher's prayer beads and some relics¹ he wants to share with Lho brag nor bzung, who has become a layman. His friend's uncle, now an ardent supporter of Communism, scolds the narrator, warning him not to involve Lho brag nor bzung in superstitious activity.

The narrator experiences an assortment of sad things late in the novel. He becomes a layman and marries a widow whose husband, a mule driver between India and Tibet, died in the conflict between Tibetan and Chinese soldiers. Later, Communist activists led the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976) in Lha sa City, encouraging the desecration and destruction of anything related to religion, including Buddha images, dharma protectors, Buddhist scripts, and various items in the Jo kang Temple.

¹ See Martin (1994) for a detailed description of Tibetan relics.

Witnessing this madness and desecrations of monasteries, an old woman fell ill and died in the narrator's neighborhood. Her only daughter was busy at the Indian border with her Chinese general husband, so only the narrator could arrange the funeral and care for her very young nephew.

A feature of *Prayers in the Wind* during this chaotic period that resonates with readers from Tibetan areas is its polyphonic narrative. Mi la ras pa¹ was a spiritual guide for both Zhi 'od kun kga' nyi ma and his pupil, the narrator, who were tightly linked by invisible and powerful spiritual beliefs. They firmly believed in an achievable mental state allowing perception of the ultimate truth of reality, liberation, and a peaceful mind. Tibetans were anguished when Red Guards² desecrated monasteries, Buddhist images, texts, and the enshrined body of Tsong kha pa.

During the Cultural Revolution, metal images from Tibetan altars were taken to the Bureau of Commencement as scrap metal, and Red Guards ordered plaster deity images tossed into the streets. The narrator was criticized for concealing his *bla ma's* deity images and prayer beads. Protecting such images irritated zealots, and, as punishment, the narrator's family was banished to a rural farm to herd communal livestock. The narrator is fond of this remote area's peaceful tranquility and freedom and does not complain. However, the narrator and his wife's relationship deteriorates once they leave the city. Shoved by a Red Guard when she attempts to prevent her husband from being taken from their home, she suffers a miscarriage. When the narrator returns, his wife is livid and exclaims, "You killed him [the infant]!" (English version:534).

Their relationship beyond restoration, the wife develops a secret relationship with a farm manager, becomes pregnant, and

¹ Mi la ras pa (1040–1123), a highly revered Tibetan yogin, famed for his austere hermetic lifestyle and the Tantric instructions he gave through songs of realization.

² Militant high school and university students placed in paramilitary units during the Cultural Revolution under the direction of the Chinese Communist Party to assist Chairman Mao deal with Party leaders who were not sufficiently revolutionary. Often wearing green jackets similar to Chinese soldier uniforms at the time, red armbands were worn on one sleeve.

dies during childbirth. The baby survived and was raised by the narrator.

Years later, the narrator was allowed to live in Lha sa City and, when he was an older man, decided to live near the Pha bong kha¹ sky burial platform and chanted for deceased souls until he died.

The author uses detail to present realistic images of people, life, norms, beliefs, and architecture. In an interview, Tse ring nor bu commented that he finds new changes in the Bar skor each time he visits, which he compares to losing his memory. He also suggests there will be no old architecture for later generations. As a writer, he maintains he is responsible for preserving cultural atmospheres, lifestyles, architecture, and ordinary people for ensuing generations to realize (FT 5).

During tensions between China and the USSR, local officers organized people to dig a bomb shelter. As I read about this, I encountered images posted on WeChat about a mountain cave teahouse.² That cave was originally a bomb shelter that had become a cultural and creative experience hall.

A similar online observation complained about the disappearance of the old teahouse (FT 12). Transformations from bomb shelter to tea house support Tse ring nor bu's concern for lost historical memories, further supported by a short online article³ describing the teahouse cave and noting general ignorance of the cave's history.

The novel's themes include redemption, honesty, trustworthiness, love, and a peaceful mind. The narrator exemplifies these qualities. While a monk, he fell in love and almost became mad when the object of his affection flirted with one of his

¹ See a full introduction of Pha bong kha at <https://bit.ly/3rAunkw> 9 February 2022.

² See Tse ring 'od zer's post on 6 October 2021. For more detail on her visit, see <https://bit.ly/3qQOWJL> 20 November 2021.

³ See <https://bit.ly/3Fpgw4O> and additional pictures of the teahouse in online articles at <https://bit.ly/3nAkCRs> and <https://bit.ly/3DMOFLe> (all 20 November 2021).

friends. Moreover, he beats his wife in a rage when she refuses to express her feelings.

Before the narrator, his tutor, and the other two monks left for the monastery, a noble lady entrusted a candy tin of jewels to Zhi 'od kun dga' nyi ma. She asked him to use the jewels to obtain a metal image of Tara for her in case she lost her life in the ongoing social chaos. The tin was taken by Tibetan soldiers, as described earlier. Later tortured during the Cultural Revolution, the lady commits suicide in her house.

The narrator risked his life to redeem a metal Tara image as the noble lady had requested. He also chanted every night while his family was sleeping. Red Guards eventually discover his chanting, the Tara image he has hidden, and his *bla ma's* prayer beads, resulting in his exile. Nevertheless, he constantly sought a peaceful mind regardless of events. Zhou (2020) comments on the kindness of each character in the novel:

在小说中，这种善是在岁月无常中证得的恒星精神，去除了执念与偏见，超越了利益与情感，闪烁着佛性的光辉，沟通了文学与宗教共同的价值追求。

This sort of kindness in the novel is an eternal spirit tested in ever-changing times, eliminating obsessiveness and prejudice, transcending benefits and emotions, and shining like an aura of Buddha nature. This may connect a common value pursued by both religion and literature (Zhou 2020:71) (my translation).

and adds:

作家试图通过建构佛教文化中的善良、宽容与悲悯等精神维度，来引导人精神世界中善的神性回归，使文学的历史叙事回归到人本身，完成了对藏族古典文化中的承接与当代阐释。

By constructing the spiritual dimensions of Buddhist kindness, tolerance, and compassion, the author has attempted to guide the recurrence of divine kindness in the spiritual world of humans; consequently, literature's historical narratives have been returned to the nature of humanity. Tibetan classical literature's inheritance of the Buddhist spirit has been accomplished in contemporary

interpretations (2020:72, my translation).

The tutor and his disciple, the narrator, achieve a peaceful mind for several days when they face death, e.g., the tutor maintains a meditative state after death. While this is powerful, it is less moving than a real-life example my grandmother (1923-2010) described. In 1958, when soldiers came to my home community, older boys and men left their homes and wives and hid in the mountains to fight. She recalled:

Community women searched for their husbands and sons among the corpses scattered in the mountains. I saw an upright corpse on the lower part of a mountain slope. In the afternoon, it was still sitting there. I was frightened, but people later said that he was a religious practitioner in a meditative state. I lost my husband and only son, who was thirteen years old. If I had kept my son with me at home, he might be alive now. But at that time, older boys at home were considered to be in danger.

This account remains fresh in my memory. What impresses me today is the practitioner's serenity displayed at the moment of his death, surrounded by gunfire and explosion.

Readers will appreciate *Prayers in the Wind's* expansive presentation of daily scripture chants and traditional lyrics, providing a realistic atmosphere. The author confides that literary critics note deep sadness in his works inherited from traditional Tibetan literature.¹ Lama Jabb (2005) has also emphasized the inheritance of traditional literary elements in themes, tones, and language styles in modern Tibetan literature.

A common theme in traditional Tibetan literature is discerning the basis of suffering. Ordinary humans experience suffering until we understand its foundation. Tshe ring nor bu presents human suffering as caused by impermanence. Regardless of their station in life, his characters experience suffering and sadness. After reading *Released Sheep*, a Chinese Academy of Social

¹ See <https://bit.ly/3x5JAvC> for an interview offered by the media platform Gaoyuan Lingjuli 'Zero Distance to the Plateau' 20 November 2021.

Sciences professor said to Tse ring nor bu on the phone, "I read your story for a week. It made me cry each time I read it, stopping for a while and continuing to read. I never had this experience before" (FT 5).

Many readers will wonder why Tshe ring nor bu writes in Chinese and not in Tibetan. He has said that his expressive ability in Tibetan is not at the level of traditional Tibetan literature. Consequently, he creates his novels in Chinese because it is convenient (FT 14).

Moreover, the author mentioned that a general theme of Chinese literature advocates material value and seeking sensory stimulus, while Tibetan literature advocates sympathy and honesty. Consequently, Tibetan literature can supplement the absence of spiritual elements in Chinese literature (FT 5). However, editor Bruce Humes comments that minority culture translated into Chinese connotes a sort of falsity: "It is, of course, interesting how the ... result resembles New Age thought."¹

In terms of translation, online commentator Françoise comments positively on the English translation: "I appreciate that the translator, although not a specialist of Tibetan, has made an effort to render Tibetan names in a readable manner that is closer to Tibetan phonetics than distorted pinyin" (FT 15).

The same commentator points out minor translation issues, such as the Chinese *chang ketou* translated as 'kowitz'. Its Tibetan equivalent is *brkyangs phyag* and should be translated as 'full-length prostration'. In the Tibetan version, *sku phyag* is used several times for the Chinese *chang ketkou*. *Sku pyag* generally indicates 'prostration' and may colloquially be used as an honorific, but it also describes ordinary monks and *bla ma*'s prostration in the Tibetan version. Consequently, the usage of *sku phyag* is confusing. Does it indicate the colloquial term, or is it an honorific?

Other minor issues in the Tibetan and English translated versions include a rough description of chewing bubblegum at Gser thang Manor. The English translation missed some information on

¹ Visit <https://bit.ly/3DEQdqE> 20 November 2021.

pages 52 and 143 of the Tibetan version. Both translations omit a lyric presented on page 112 of the Chinese version. On the same page of the English version mentioned above, the English translator inserts a lyric absent in both the Tibetan and Chinese versions.

The Tibetan and English versions both read fluently. The English version offers explanations for outsiders to the Tibetan cultural world in the first three pages, making it more accessible as they read the novel. If Wylie had been offered for the transliterated terms, it would have helped readers understand the original Tibetan, e.g., Françoise asserts, "Zhyiö looks so unfamiliar I cannot figure out what the Tibetan original might be" (FT 14).

The Tibetan version is vivid and authentic with its colloquial expressions, daily scripture chants, and traditional lyrics. It is impossible to fathom the scriptures and dharma lyrics without the Tibetan version in comprehensively understanding this novel, and it also explains its popularity among Tibetan readers.

After five years of preparation and writing, the author states:

为了完成这部长篇小说，光收集、查阅资料，走访、调研，我花了三年的时间，通过创作《祭语风中》，我深切地感受到一个作家平时储备知识的重要性，创作中不能存有侥幸心理，一定要踏踏实实。

I spent three years collecting and reading materials, interviewing people, and investigating to complete this novel. In creating *Prayers in the Wind*, I profoundly sensed the importance of knowledge a writer should possess and maintain integrity and diligence in the process of writing (Hu and Ciren Luobu 2016:119, my translation).

Prayers in the Wind's panoramic presentation of Tibetan culture, history, and people, provides insights into Tibetan religious and secular life in the pre-1949 period and social transitions in the 1950s-1970s. From a monk's perspective, individual suffering and hope from social-political changes offer objective descriptions that add to the novel's significance. In presenting this version of recent social history in three languages, readers can better appreciate what Tibetan writers envisioned and presented before the 2020s.

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TIBETAN TERMS

'brug mo skyid འབྲུག་མོ་སྐྱིད།

'jigs med dbang grags

འཇིགས་མེད་དབང་གཤགས།

bla ma ལྷ་མ།

brkyangs phyag བརྒྱུད་ས་ཕྱག།

chab mdo ཆབ་མདོ།

Lama Jabb, bla ma skyabs

ལྷ་མ་སྐྱབས།

lha sa ལྷ་ས།

lho brag nor bzang

ལྷོ་བྲག་ནོར་བཟང།

mi la ras pa མེ་ལ་རས་པ།

nor dpal zur རྣོར་དཔལ་ཕུར།

pad+ma rig 'dzin བཤམ་རིག་འཛིན།

pho ba ཕོ་བ།

pyag ཕྱག།

Qomolangma; jo mo glang ma

རྫོ་མོ་གླང་མ།

rdo rje rgya mtshan རྫོ་རྗེ་རྒྱ་མཚན།

Sertang, gser thang གཤམ་ར་ཐང།

sne mo ལྷོ་མོ།

Tsering Norbu, tshe ring nor

ཚེ་རིང་ནོར་བུ།

tshwa tshwa ཚ་ཚ།

yi dam ཡི་དམ།

zhi 'od kun dga' nyi ma ཞི་འོད་ཀུན་

དགའ་ཉི་མ།

CHINESE TERMS

2009 *Nian Zhongguo*

Duanpian Xiaoshuoji

2009 年中国短篇小说集

21 *Shiji Zhongguo Dangdai*

Wenxue 21

世纪中国当代文学

Changdu 昌都

Ciren Luobu 次仁罗布

chang ketou 长磕头

Fangcao 芳草

Li Jiajun 李佳军

Lu Xun 鲁迅

Mao 毛

Nimu 尼木

Wanmerenzeng 完么仁增

Wusizang 乌斯藏

Xiaoshuo xuankan 小说选刊

Xiaoshuo yuebao 小说月报